

Utilization of Performance-Based Assessment

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ABSTRACT

Performance-based assessment is an integral component of any educational process; hence, teachers must measure learners' competencies accurately. The study aimed to determine the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers in public schools, a large-sized division in Central Philippines, for the school year 2024-2025, as a basis for a capability-building plan. Descriptive research was conducted, and a 45-item survey questionnaire was used to gather data from 35 MAPEH teachers to determine the utilization of performance-based assessment. The results revealed that most of the respondents were young professionals under 40 years old, the majority were female, they had more than nine (9) years of experience teaching MAPEH, and had attended few training/workshops related to MAPEH. Overall, the extent of teachers' utilization of performance-based assessments according to process-based, performance-based, and product-based assessments was great. The extent of utilization of performance-based assessment in the areas of product-based and performance-based, when grouped by age, sex, length of service, and number of training/workshops, was great. At the same time, it was very significant in process-based, concerning age, length of service, and number of training/workshops. Further, a significant difference was found in the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers across three (3) areas when compared according to their length of service in teaching MAPEH. This finding calls for the DepEd HRTD team and supervisors in MAPEH to work together to develop a continuous professional development program and allocate more funds for the learning resources for the MAPEH curriculum.

Keywords: Performance-based assessment, utilization, product-based, performance-based, process-based

How to Cite:

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INTRODUCTION

Assessment is a key process for monitoring student progress, evaluating learning standards, and developing twenty-first-century skills. It encourages self-reflection and accountability while helping teachers profile student performance based on curriculum competencies. As emphasized in DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015, assessments must be appropriate for diverse learners across various contexts. To achieve effective learning outcomes, educators must select suitable assessment methods that holistically measure learner abilities and promote self-directed learning. Performance-based assessments—covering product-based, performance-based, and process-based approaches—allow students to demonstrate what they know and can do through final outputs, applied skills, and real-world tasks (Adjei et al., 2020; Zamora, 2023).

Despite the benefits of performance-based assessments, several challenges hinder their proper implementation. In the research locale, 40% of MAPEH teachers are teaching outside their specialization, which affects their ability to apply appropriate assessments across the subject's four distinct disciplines. Observations also show that some non-specialized teachers lack sufficient resources and training, leading to minimal or substandard assessment practices. Additionally, factors such as age, limited experience, and inadequate professional development contribute to teachers no longer following assessment standards, resulting in reduced quality of learning evaluations.

Considering the above-mentioned observation, the researcher is motivated to investigate the utilization of performance-based assessment and propose a capability-building plan to ensure teachers are adequately equipped to effectively implement the K to 12 MAPEH programs.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to determine the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers in public schools in a district of a large division in Central Philippines for the school year 2024-2025 as a basis for a capability-building plan. Specifically, this sought to answer the following questions: 1) the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, length of service in teaching MAPEH, and number of trainings/workshops attended in MAPEH; 2) the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers according to the product-based, performance-based, and process-based; and 3) the significant difference in the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance-based assessment (PBA) is widely recognized as an effective contemporary assessment approach because it bridges the gap between what students know and how they use that knowledge. It enables learners to demonstrate their understanding by solving real-world problems rather than merely selecting answers, fostering creativity and deeper thinking (Gyamfi et al., 2023). Despite its potential, many teachers still have limited knowledge of PBA forms and implementation, even when they have some background in assessment. This gap highlights the need for training that updates teachers on new assessment techniques and technology-supported tools (Anu, 2022), ensuring that assessments more accurately reflect student abilities.

A major component of PBA is product-based assessment, which evaluates learning through outputs such as essays, models, artworks, or prototypes (Gelborion, 2023). This approach encourages students to work creatively and to apply what they know in a tangible form. It shifts the focus from simply recalling facts to demonstrating understanding through authentic tasks that resemble real-world activities. Gelborion (2023) also notes that product-based assessment can increase students' motivation and foster skills essential for today's learners. Researchers further stress the importance of following clear stage as planning, production, and evaluation—to make the assessment process fair and aligned with learning goals (Yustiana & Kusumadewi, 2019).

Performance-based assessment also involves examining how students apply skills across different areas, making it an authentic measure of competence (Kone, 2021; Heydarnejad et al., 2022). Process-based assessment expands this idea by focusing on the steps students take as they complete tasks, often through projects or simulations. These methods are designed to evaluate practical skills needed in future careers. However, many teachers encounter difficulties such as limited time, heavy workloads, and a lack of training or materials, which often prevent the full implementation of PBA (Sundeme, 2019; Salma & Prastikawati, 2022).

Teacher-related factors also influence how effectively PBA is used. More experienced teachers tend to apply assessment strategies with greater confidence, especially in areas requiring analysis and judgment (Al Atoum et al., 2022). Age has also been linked to greater stability and comfort with assessment tasks, as older teachers generally show more balanced decision-making

(Pranoto et al., 2021). Some studies point to differences in assessment practices based on gender, though findings vary across contexts (Marquez, 2023).

Research involving MAPEH teachers shows that their competence in PBA and product-based assessment varies widely. Some teachers are skilled in evaluating performance tasks, but others face challenges stemming from limited specialization, lack of materials, and minimal opportunities for professional development (Capanas, 2019; Daga, 2020; Culajara, 2021). More recent studies also indicate that attending seminars or training does not always guarantee better implementation of PBA, suggesting that teachers may need ongoing and more targeted support (Agawin & Alferez, 2024; Magallanes & Villocino, 2024; Capangyarihan, 2025; Vallo, 2025).

Despite these challenges, PBA remains an effective way to assess higher-order thinking, procedural knowledge, and authentic learning. When paired with clear criteria like rubrics and success indicators, it helps students better understand their progress and encourages them to take a more active role in their learning (Villarta et al., 2021; Masaoay & Litao, 2021). For teachers, effective use of PBA means designing meaningful learning tasks, offering timely feedback, and continuously improving their assessment practices to support the development of essential 21st-century skills.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive research design to determine the extent of teachers' use of performance-based assessment in public schools within a district of a large division in Central Philippines for School Year 2024–2025 as the basis for a capability-building plan. Descriptive research, defined as a scientific approach that observes and characterizes a subject's behavior influenced by various factors (Siedlecki, 2020), is appropriate for examining existing conditions, practices, beliefs, processes, and emerging trends. The researcher deemed this design suitable because it allows for the systematic gathering of information about the current characteristics of the study, enabling sound professional judgments and well-informed recommendations through focused analysis and interpretation of the collected data.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 35 MAPEH/PE teachers. Total enumeration was considered; hence, purposive sampling was used. Purposive sampling is a type of non-probability sampling where researchers select study participants from the community at their own discretion (Ames et al., 2019). Researchers use purposive sampling to access a particular subset of people, as all survey participants are selected because they fit a particular profile.

Instruments

This study utilized a self-made questionnaire consisting of two parts: Part I gathered respondents' demographic profiles, while Part II measured the extent of performance-based assessment utilization across product-based, performance-based, and process-based areas using a 5-point scale. To ensure validity, the instrument was evaluated by three experts with advanced academic and professional backgrounds in MAPEH, curriculum implementation, and educational research, and its content was assessed using the criteria of Good and Scates, resulting in an excellent validity index of 4.83. Reliability was established through Cronbach's alpha, administered to 30 non-respondent MAPEH teachers, yielding a coefficient of 0.826, which falls under the "good" category, confirming that the instrument is both valid and reliable for the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

For the smoother conduct of the study, the researcher employed the following procedures: The researcher sent a letter of request for the conduct of the study to the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Negros Oriental. Upon approval, a separate letter was also sent to the school head of the schools concerned, which is attached to the approved letter from the superintendent. After securing the approval for the second request, the researcher sent the research instrument to the respondents using Google Forms. At the same time, a hard copy was provided to MAPEH teachers who had difficulty accessing the form electronically. The researcher also included his contact number and Messenger account in the research instrument in case teachers encountered difficulty answering the instrument. Google Sheets used to retrieve the data for those who answered online, while the researcher gathered the data personally for those who answered in hard copies.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical schemes and frequency count and percentage to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, length of service teaching MAPEH, and training/workshop attended in MAPEH.

Objective No. 2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers.

Objective No. 3 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant difference in the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers when grouped and compared according to the variables.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher attended to the respondents' voluntary participation, informed consent, risk of harm, confidentiality, and anonymity as a priority in preventing human rights violations during the research process. Participation in the study was voluntary, and the respondents had the right to withdraw without any consequences. The researcher informed the respondents that the study was for academic purposes only. To ensure confidentiality, only the researcher had access to the research data. The researcher also handed out consent and assent forms to confirm their voluntary participation in the study.

Additionally, throughout the study, the researcher adhered very strictly to the rules and policies of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 to ensure that security measures were in place to safeguard personal and sensitive information. Such a commitment to ethical standards creates trust among participants and indicates the integrity of the research findings. Compliance with these guidelines is intended to maintain the highest level of professionalism in our research process. In addition, they consented and were informed before the data-gathering instrument was conducted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1

Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 40 years old)	20	57.10
	Older (40 years old and above)	15	42.90
Sex	Male	12	34.30
	Female	23	65.70
Length of Service in Teaching MAPEH	Shorter (less than 10 years)	15	42.90
	Longer (10 years and above)	20	57.10
Number of Training/ Workshop Attended in MAPEH	Few (less than 5)	26	74.30
	Many (5 and above)	9	25.70
	Total	35	100.00

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, length of service, and trainings attended in MAPEH. The result showed that 20, or 57.10%, are younger respondents below 40 years old, while 15, or 42.90%, are older respondents, or

those 40 years old and above. Regarding sex, 12, or 34.30%, are male respondents, while 23, or 65.70%, are female. Regarding the length of service in teaching MAPEH, 15, or 42.90%, of the respondents had served for less than 10 years, while 20, or 57.10%, had served for more than 10 years. Further, for trainings/workshops attended in MAPEH, 26, or 74.30%, of the respondents have attended a few trainings, while 9, or 25.70%, have attended many trainings and workshops.

The result indicates that the younger group contributed a larger number of respondents, the majority were females, and a significant number of them had served for more than 9 years and mostly had attended a few trainings and workshops related to MAPEH. It is said that mature and female teachers with more teaching experience tend to have greater ability in delivering instruction; however, without appropriate training related to MAPEH, some learning competencies were not successfully achieved, as the quality of teaching greatly influences the quality of learning. The finding supports Costales (2022), who reported that most teacher-respondents were female in their early adulthood with a BS degree and a master's degree; however, they lacked specialized training in specific learning areas. Capanas (2019) also reported that many MAPEH teachers had longer years in the teaching service but received minimal opportunities for professional development.

Table 2

Extent of Utilization of Performance-Based Assessment of Teachers according to the Product-Based

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I use product-based assessment to...</i>		
1. determine learning acquisition of the basic knowledge and skills in music.	4.03	Great Extent
2. evaluate learners' knowledge of the salient features of the arts.	4.09	Great Extent
3. gauge learners' understanding of the importance of exercise.	4.34	Great Extent
4. determine management skills in personal health.	4.34	Great Extent
5. measure their skills in Philippine folk songs.	3.54	Great Extent
6. know their knowledge of Philippine arts and cultural traditions.	3.71	Great Extent
7. measure their learning levels on various physical fitness activities.	4.11	Great Extent
8. determine their decision-making skills on personal hygiene and nutrition.	4.17	Great Extent
9. know their talents in playing basic musical instruments.	3.77	Great Extent
10. assess their creativity skills in making posters, slogans, etc.	4.17	Great Extent
11. know their talents in folk, ethnic, and traditional dances.	3.69	Great Extent
12. determine their basic knowledge and skills on first aid.	3.83	Great Extent
13. identify their talents in sports.	4.37	Great Extent
14. know their innovative skills in delivering reports and presentations.	3.77	Great Extent
15. determine their communication skills during classroom discussions.	4.09	Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.00	Great Extent

Table 2 presents the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers in product-based settings. It obtained an overall mean score of 4.00, which was interpreted to a great extent. This indicates that respondents, to some extent, utilized product-based assessment to ensure final products or learning created by students are measured accordingly. Veering closely, item 13 obtained the highest mean of 4.37, or to a great extent, using product-based assessment to identify their talents in sports.

On the other hand, the lowest mean score of 3.54, or to a great extent, was obtained by item 5 when using product-based assessment to measure their skills in Philippine folk songs. This implies that most respondents showed less compliance with using product-based assessments to measure learners' skills in Philippine folk songs. This lack of compliance is attributed to the unavailability of song assessment tools, time constraints in developing specific product-based assessments, a shortage of music materials, and the respondents' limited knowledge of music. These factors collectively hinder the effective implementation of product-based assessments, suggesting that improvements in resources and training are necessary to enhance compliance and ultimately better evaluate learners' skills in this area. Addressing these challenges could lead to more effective assessment practices in teaching Philippine folk songs.

The result supports Tabuena et al. (2021), revealing that teachers greatly complied with using product-based assessment in evaluating students' music performance.

Table 3

Extent of Utilization of Performance-Based Assessment of Teachers according to the Performance-Based

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I use performance-based assessment to...</i>		

1. demonstrate their mastery of the music lesson.	3.91	Great Extent
2. express my own ideas on Philippine arts through question-and-answer.	4.03	Great Extent
3. show abilities in written analysis and explanation of health-related issues.	4.06	Great Extent
4. apply skills to physical fitness exercises.	4.51	Very Great Extent
5. show their skills in doing projects and portfolios in the arts.	4.43	Great Extent
6. gain confidence to speak in individual and group reports in music.	4.11	Great Extent
7. facilitate cooperation among learners in group activities in physical education.	4.31	Great Extent
8. show skills in making multimedia presentations in music and the arts.	3.83	Great Extent
9. apply skills in conducting interviews on community and environmental health.	3.89	Great Extent
10. expose the learners to solving problems and proving theorems.	3.89	Great Extent
11. show personal time management skills.	4.09	Great Extent
12. allow learners to advocate for health and disease prevention campaigns.	4.20	Great Extent
13. encourage learners to join in community outreach programs.	4.17	Great Extent
14. deliver their talents in dancing and singing.	4.51	Very Great Extent
15. allow learners to participate in sports.	4.54	Very Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.17	Great Extent

Table 3 shows the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers. The results showed an overall mean score of 4.17, which was interpreted to a great extent. This indicates that the respondents, to some extent, can implement various performance-based assessments to measure learners' actual performances. Further, item 15 obtained the highest mean of 4.54, or to a great extent, when using performance-based assessment to allow learners to participate in sports.

Meanwhile, the lowest mean score of 3.83, or to a great extent, was obtained by item 8 on teachers' utilization of performance-based assessment to show skills in making multimedia presentations in music and the arts. The result suggests strengthening performance-based activities, particularly multimedia music and arts presentations. Lack of resources for technology, music, and artistic materials, as well as fewer skills in multimedia presentations, were barriers to doing so. These barriers hindered the effective implementation of performance-based activities, emphasizing the need for improved access to resources and training. The result is supported by Daga (2020), who states that MAPEH teachers' competencies in conducting performance-based assessment in music and the arts were great.

Table 4

Extent of Utilization of Performance-Based Assessment of Teachers According to the Process-based

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I use performance-based assessment to.....</i>		
1. enhance their knowledge and understanding of music.	4.23	Great Extent
2. improve their appreciation and interest in arts and cultural heritage.	4.14	Great Extent
3. develop critical thinking skills for health issues.	4.34	Great Extent
4. promote cooperative learning among learners in physical education activities.	4.34	Great Extent
5. improve problem-solving skills.	4.14	Great Extent
6. enhance understanding of the proper nutrition and eating habits.	4.34	Great Extent
7. sustain interest in the classroom instruction in the arts.	4.29	Great Extent
8. promote understanding of environmental safety and disaster preparedness.	4.34	Great Extent
9. address students' diverse learning needs in music and arts.	4.20	Great Extent
10. apply learning in a real-life situation.	4.37	Great Extent
11. promote the physical and mental health of the learners.	4.43	Great Extent
12. promote a sense of responsibility and concern for others.	4.37	Great Extent
13. develop physical and motor skills through games and sports.	4.54	Very Great Extent
14. improve social communication skills.	4.37	Great Extent
15. enhance technological skills in performing learning tasks.	4.17	Great Extent
Overall Mean	4.31	Great Extent

Table 4 divulges the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers in process-based assessment. It shows that the respondents obtained an overall mean score of 4.31 and interpreted it greatly. The data indicate that the respondents

exhibit good abilities in using process-based assessments. Investigating the table further, item 13 obtained the highest mean of 4.54, or to a very great extent, using process-based assessment to develop physical and motor skills through games and sports.

On the other hand, the lowest mean score of 4.14, or to a great extent, was obtained by items 2 and 5. Item 2 uses process-based assessment to improve their appreciation and interest in arts and cultural heritage, and item 5 uses process-based assessment to improve problem-solving skills. Both items are interpreted to a great extent. The findings entail that the respondents require a more profound understanding of arts and culture to implement appropriate process-based activities successfully. The reason is that many respondents lack sufficient skills in arts and culture, as they seldom received training in this field. In addition, the results suggest that respondents need to enhance their expertise in creating process-based activities that improve learners' problem-solving skills in MAPEH. By doing so, learners may effectively engage in meaningful learning experiences.

The result opposes that of Al Atoum et al. (2022), who found that the utilization level of assessment strategies among arts education teachers was moderate, highlighting the use of clear standards in assessing their artwork and developing their ability in observation, analysis, explanation, problem-solving, and judgments about the performances of the learners.

Table 5

Difference in the Extent of Utilization of Performance-Based Assessment of Teachers according to the Product-Based when grouped and compared according to Age, Sex, Length of Service in Teaching, MAPEH, and Trainings/Workshops Attended in MAPEH

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	20	15.28	95.50	0.069	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	15	21.63				
Sex	Male	12	20.17	112.00	0.381	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	23	16.87				
Length of Service in Teaching MAPEH	Shorter	15	13.43	81.50	0.021	0.05	Significant
	Longer	20	21.43				
Trainings/ Workshops in MAPEH	Few	26	16.23	71.00	0.086	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	9	23.11				

Table 5 summarizes the difference in the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers in product-based teaching according to age, sex, length of service in teaching MAPEH, and training/workshops in MAPEH. The table shows that the computed p-values of the variables age, sex, and training/workshops in MAPEH are 0.069, 0.381, and 0.086, respectively; greater than the 0.05 significance level and thus interpreted as insignificant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers in product-based learning when grouped and compared according to age, sex, and training/workshops attended in MAPED is accepted.

The finding implies that the extent of utilization of product-based assessment varies according to age, sex, and the number of training/workshops attended in MAPEH. This suggests that different demographic factors, such as age and sex, along with the level of training received, have nothing to do with how effectively MAPEH teachers use product-based assessments. Most MAPEH teachers exhibited the same knowledge of using strategies in product-based assessment activities irrespective of their age, gender, and the type of training attended.

However, for the variable length of service in teaching MAPEH, the computed p-value is 0.021, which is less than the 0.05 significance level and thus interpreted as significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers in product-based learning when grouped and compared according to training/workshops in MAPEH is rejected.

The finding implies that the extent to which teachers utilize performance-based assessments in product-based learning when grouped and compared according to length of service in teaching MAPEH varies. This is because respondents with more years in teaching MAPEH had already gained various strategies, methods, and experiences in conducting assessments compared to novice teachers. The more years in teaching, the greater the mastery in using product-based assessment compared to teachers new to teaching. This experience allows them to implement more effective process-based assessment techniques, leading to better evaluation of learners' performance in MAPEH. The finding contradicts that of Daga (2020), who found no significant

difference in MAPEH teachers' utilization of product-based assessments and delivering reports and presentations based on their length of service.

The result is supported by Costales (2022) on teachers' utilization of strategies on product-based activities, wherein there was no significant difference in age, sex, and the number of seminars and trainings when assessing learners' performance through product-based activities.

Table 6

Difference in the Extent of Utilization of Performance-Based Assessment of Teachers according to the Performance-Based when grouped and compared according to Age, Sex, Length of Service in Teaching, MAPEH, and Trainings/Workshops Attended in MAPEH

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	20	16.18	113.50	0.227	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	15	20.43				
Sex	Male	12	19.92	115.00	0.440	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	23	17.00				
Length of Service in Teaching MAPEH	Shorter	15	13.17	77.50	0.014	0.05	Significant
	Longer	20	21.63				
Trainings/Workshops in MAPEH	Few	26	16.17	69.50	0.073	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	9	23.38				

Table 6 reviews the difference in the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers in performance-based assessment according to age, sex, length of service in teaching MAPEH, and training/workshops in MAPEH.

Variable age, sex, and training/workshops in MAPEH have calculated p-values of 0.227, 0.440, and 0.073, respectively. These values are higher than the 0.05 significance level and therefore considered non-significant. Consequently, it is agreed that there is no difference in how teachers use performance-based assessments in the field when grouped and contrasted by age, sex, and training/workshops attended in MAPEH.

This implies that the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment does not differ when compared according to their ages, sex, and the number of training/workshops attended in MAPEH. This suggests that factors such as age, gender, and the amount of training or workshops attended have nothing to do with how teachers use performance-based assessments in MAPEH. Therefore, these assessments appear consistent across different demographic groups because they utilized performance-based activities to the same extent. Capangyarihan (2025) supports the finding, revealing no significant difference in MAPEH teachers' utilization of performance-based activities when grouped according to their age, sex, educational attainment, and training attended.

However, the calculated p-value for the variable length of service in teaching MAPEH is 0.014, which is below the 0.05 level of significance and is therefore considered significant. Thus, the hypothesis that there is no discernible variation in how teachers use performance-based evaluation when categorized and contrasted based on training/workshops in MAPEH is disproved.

The result indicates that teachers with more experience in teaching MAPEH are better at conducting performance-based activities than neophyte teachers, based on their mean ranks. This advantage is because of the experiences they gain over time. The experiences accumulated over the years enable seasoned teachers to develop effective strategies and techniques for executing performance-based activities compared to less experienced educators. The finding supports Marquez (2023), who discovered no discernible differences in teachers' procedures and practices for using performance-based assessment regarding length of service.

Table 7

Difference in the Extent of Utilization of Performance-Based Assessment of Teachers according to the Process-Based when grouped and compared according to Age, Sex, Length of Service in Teaching, MAPEH, and Trainings/Workshops Attended in MAPEH

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
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Age	Younger	20	14.93	88.50	0.039	Significant
	Older	15	22.10			
Sex	Male	12	21.04	101.50	0.208	Not Significant
	Female	23	16.41			
Length of Service in Teaching MAPEH	Shorter	15	13.87	88.00	0.039	0.05
	Longer	20	21.63			
Trainings/ Workshops in MAPEH	Few	26	15.52	52.50	0.013	Significant
	Many	9	25.17			

Table 7 shows the difference in the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers in process-based assessment according to age, sex, length of service in teaching MAPEH, and training/workshops in MAPEH.

The computed p-value of the variable sex is 0.208, greater than the 0.05 significance level and thus interpreted as insignificant. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers in process-based learning when grouped and compared according to sex.

The finding implies that the extent of utilization of process-based assessment of teachers does not vary when compared to sex. Male and female MAPEH teachers use process-based assessment methods at similar rates. This is because they have the same understanding of how to conduct process-based performance tasks. Therefore, gender does not appear to influence how these assessment techniques are utilized and implemented by teachers. The finding is supported by Al Atoum et al. (2022), who showed no significant difference between the mean scores in the utilization level of assessment strategies among arts education teachers compared to gender.

However, for the variables of age, length of service in teaching MAPEH, and training/workshops in MAPEH, the computed p-values are 0.039, 0.039, and 0.013, respectively; these values are less than the 0.05 level of significance and are therefore interpreted as significant. This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers in process-based when grouped and compared according to age, length of service in teaching MAPEH, and training/workshops in MAPEH.

The result implies that the extent of utilization of performance-based assessment of teachers in process-based assessment varies when grouped and compared according to age, length of service in teaching MAPEH, and training/workshops in MAPEH. This means that factors such as age, experience, and professional development opportunities contribute to how teachers utilize and implement process-based assessments in MAPEH. This is because senior MAPEH teachers with more years in teaching and abundant training have gained rich experiences, resulting in mastery in using process-based assessment compared to their counterparts. The result contradicts that of Magallanes and Villocino (2024), who revealed no significant difference in MAPEH teachers' utilization of process-based performance tasks of the learners when compared according to age, length of service, training, and seminars attended.

CONCLUSION

The study showed that most of the respondents were young and mostly female, with several years of teaching experience but limited opportunities to attend MAPEH-related training. Overall, they demonstrated a strong use of performance-based assessment across product-based, performance-based, and process-based areas. Differences in how they applied these assessments were noticeable in certain groups—particularly in product-based and performance-based tasks among teachers with varying lengths of service, and in process-based tasks among teachers of different ages, years of experience, and training backgrounds—while sex showed no significant influence. From these findings, the study concluded that many teachers still struggled with cultural knowledge, folk song appreciation, and multimedia skills, and that their performance-based assessment practices reflected the diversity of their experiences. It also became clear that teachers with more years in MAPEH, and those with more training, were better equipped to handle product-based and process-based assessments.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To help address these gaps, the study recommends several capacity-building initiatives, such as workshops on Philippine folk arts, training on digital and multimedia tools for music and arts, and activities that reconnect teachers with Philippine cultural heritage. Continuous knowledge-sharing, regular benchmarking, and encouraging teachers to pursue graduate studies were also suggested to strengthen their abilities and confidence in implementing performance-based assessments.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors confirm that there are no conflicts of interest related to the conduct, writing, or publication of this research. All procedures and interpretations were done independently, with no financial, professional, or personal influence affecting the outcomes of the study

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